

THE PATTERN OF RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION IN AUSTRALIA IN 2036

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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to provide a preliminary forecast of religious affiliations in Australia. The forecast is made on the basis of religious affiliation at five-year intervals in the Census of Population and Housing from 1971-2021. A simple linear regression is used and confidence intervals calculated. Results indicated that by 2036, Christians would comprise around 40.3% of the population (95%CI [33.8, 46.8]); those with No Religion would comprise around 40.7% (95%CI [33.4, 48.0]); and Other Religions would comprise 14.8% (95%CI [11.8, 17.8]). The results suggest changes in the religious landscape of the population that will most likely affect the national mindset.

Keywords

Census, Australia, religious affiliation, Christian, no religion, other religions

I. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this report is to provide a preliminary forecast of religious affiliation in Australia. It is well-known Christianity has been the dominant religious affiliation in Australia but of late there has been an increase in those persons with no religion or persons of other religions (i.e., Buddhism, Hinduism, Islam, Judaism).

Figure 1 Religious affiliation in Australia: 1971 and 2021

The change in these three main groups in the national Census of Population and Housing from 1971 to 2021 is highlighted in Figure 1. Christianity has declined from 86.2% of the population in 1971 to 43.9% in 2021, whereas Other Religions increased from 0.8% to 10%, and those with No Religion have climbed from 6.7% to 38.9%. Table 1 lists the proportional representation of Christians, No Religion and Other Religions from 1971-2021.

TABLE 1

Religious affiliation in Australia, 1971-2021

Year	Christianity	Other religions	No religion
1971	86.2	0.8	6.7
1976	78.6	1	8.3
1981	76.4	1.4	10.8
1986	73	2	12.7
1991	74	2.6	12.9
1996	70.9	3.5	16.6
2001	68	4.9	16.7
2006	63.9	5.6	19.3
2011	61.1	7.2	23.1
2016	52.1	8.2	30.1
2021	43.9	10	38.9

Source: Australian Bureau of Statistics, Religious affiliation in Australia July 2022

II. METHOD

A forecast through to 2036 of future religious affiliation was based on the historical data from 1971-2021 in Table 1 (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2022). A line of best fit indicating the 95 percent confidence level was determined. Additional statistics are provided in the Appendix.

III. RESULTS

By 2036, it is forecast that the proportion of the population with No religion is likely to equal Christianity for the first time but there will also be a situation where almost 15% of the population will be adherents of other religions. The projections are summarised in Table 2 and illustrated with 95% confidence intervals in Figure 2.

For instance, it is forecast that Christianity will comprise 40.7% \pm 6.4%, Other Religions are forecasted to be 11.8% \pm 3.0% and No Religion is forecasted to be 40.7% \pm 7.29%. Further results and statistical values are provided in the Appendix.

TABLE 2

Religious affiliation in Australia: 2026-2036

	Christianity	Other religions	No religion
2026	47.4%	11.6%	35.2%
2031	43.9%	13.2%	38.0%
2036	40.3%	14.9%	40.7%

Figure 2 Religious affiliation in Australia: 2036 (with 95% confidence interval)

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusion from this forecast is the further decline of Christianity. One may speculate that as societal norms changed, it became more socially acceptable for many to “switch” from Christianity to No Religion. One cannot be certain whether it will reach its nadir by 2036.

What one can say is that by 2036 Australia will in all likelihood be a decidedly non-Christian nation but it will still remain religious because Christian plus Other Religion will total around 55.2%.

Of course, this analysis has some limitations. It relies firstly on the completeness and accuracy of the Census data. By way of background, the number of people who answered the religion question in 2021 was 93.1% of the population. Secondly, the

method of forecasting overlooks many complexities, such as (a) migration - 39.9% of recent migrants 2017-2021 are in the category of Other Religion; (b) the age structure within religious groups - Christianity is dominated by older age cohorts (56.8% of those aged 55-74 and 69.4% of those aged 75 years and over are Christian); (c) likely differences in birth rates across religions (44% of those aged 10-24 years and 46.5% of those aged 25-39 years are No Religion); and (d) differences within the Christian cohort, with some groups showing increases (e.g., 76,100 Christianity not formally defined; or 17,400 Greek Orthodox) and others a decline (-604,900 Anglican; or -215,900 Catholic; or -196,900 Uniting Church). Finally, there are more complex demographic approaches that could be applied than a simple linear regression.

It is not a remarkable statement that these findings have implications for the future fabric of Australian society and its ethos. The move away from Christianity brings with it a change in the mindset of the population due to heterogeneous values, ethics or purpose in life.

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Other papers in this series:

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APPENDIX: Statistical values

Christian forecast 2026-2036

No religion forecast 2026-2036

Other religions forecast 2026-2036

Statistic	Christian	Other religions	No religion
Alpha	0.00	1.00	0.25
Beta	0.00	0.75	0.00
Gamma	0.00	0.00	0.00
MASE	1.11	0.88	2.45
SMAPE	0.07	0.08	0.14
MAE	3.73	0.60	4.08
RMSE	4.20	0.62	4.89

Explanations:

1. Alpha (base value) - the smoothing value between 0 and 1 that controls the weighting of data points. The higher the value, the more weight is given to recent data.
2. Beta (trend value) - the value between 0 and 1 that determines the trend calculation. The higher the value, the more weight is given to recent trends.
3. Gamma (seasonality value) - the value between 0 and 1 that controls the seasonality of the ETS forecast. The higher the value, the more weight is given to the recent seasonal period.
4. MASE (mean absolute scaled error) - a measure of the forecast accuracy. MASE<1 implies that the forecast performs better.
5. SMAPE (symmetric mean absolute percentage error) - a measure of accuracy based on percentage or relative errors. SMAPE has a lower bound of 0% and an upper bound of 200%.
6. MAE (mean absolute error) - measures the average magnitude of the prediction errors, regardless of their direction. A common measure of the forecast error.
7. RMSE (root mean square error) - a measure of the differences between the predicted and observed values (Sources for explanations: ablebits.com and numxl.com Retrieved October 2022)